

Near-home bias, territorial stigmatization and Eurocentrism in country-risk assessments for FDI allocation

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Abstract:

The given study provides an analysis of FDI network dynamics after coronavirus outbreak. Shares of FDI stock from individual nation-states to separate country-level destinations have been analysed by computing local indicators of spatial association (LISA).

FDI near-home bias has been identified in the IMF Coordinated Direct Investment Survey results. It could explain divergence investment allocation to various countries after coronavirus outbreak (leading to temporary self-isolation of many economies).

Moreover, this non-uniform distribution of FDI changes between 2020 and 2021 was found to have cluster patterns beyond first-order neighbours. In particular, many European countries received increasing FDI share from economies located at the other side of their continent, at the same time these investors took their capital out of most non-European countries.

These clusters could persist in many cases due to institutional and cultural considerations factored into investors' decision-making, which could lead to territorial stigmatization. Reasons for this willingness to finance projects located in neighboring countries could include political stability, which communicate confidence to capital holders.

Keywords:

LISA (local indicators of spatial association), FDI network, near-home bias, portfolio adjustment, territorial stigmatization, coronavirus restrictions, Coordinated Direct Investment Survey, clustering, qualculation, decision-making.

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Introduction

In contemporary post-scarcity attention economy (especially during overproduction crises periods) there is abundance of foreign direct investment (FDI) variants for an investor: he or she could direct money to various assets worldwide — all the funds to the same «basket» or diversify his or her portfolio.

From attention economy point of view, one could regard FDI assignment process around the world as investors stopping their selection on some country set. By allocating capital to addressees deemed worthy of attention financial institutions reveal their preference for these destinations.

Remaining important to many phenomena, preferences play especially decisive role in the context of «reshoring» policies pursued by many developed countries. These state efforts target investors' behavior, so relevant measures could include stimulating transnational companies to reindustrialize European and American territories instead of maintaining facilities overseas.

Along with static preferences, it would be important to analyze their dynamics after impactful events. For instance, a shift in FDI preferences could be witnessed after coronavirus outbreak, because the pandemic restrictions reshaped global value chains and made companies redefine their strategies of international presence. In particular, some firms reevaluated the usefulness of various modes of market entry, including investment in domestic or nearby facilities (as compared to FDI to developing countries and exporting goods from there to consumers in a domestic country).

Although this dynamic is heterogenous, some regularity could exist in FDI rebalancing after coronavirus outbreak. The given study attempts at finding a spatial structure in outward investment stock changes and provide some examples of these patterns.

Network view of FDI

This type of phenomena could be studied more thoroughly if situated in a network model, so many scholars adopted the network perspective on FDI (Bolívar, Casanueva, Castro 2019; Chin-Lung, Wen-Chang 2009; Damgaard, Elkjaer 2017; De Masi, Ricchiuti 2020; Gorgoni, Amighini, Smith 2018; Koskinen, Caimo, Lomi 2015; Rytter Sunesen, Jeppesen, Theilgaard, Kristensen, Grunfelder 2018). From this point of view flows in a graph represent summarized transactions between investors and destination object or investment project.

Usually in international statistics this description methodology is used at the country level: investment transactions are aggregated into international flows (along the edges of this graph) and all the investors from a domestic economy are united into one FDI source node. On the other side of an edge investments received are also summarized into a single value, which characterizes a sink node - FDI inflow.

Fig. 1. Outward FDI stock from France registered by the OECD.

Fig. 2. Outward FDI stock from Germany registered by the OECD.

E.g. this network approach has been practiced by the OECD data collectors (OECD Data n.d.). In particular, this database allows for computing the share of the overall FDI outflow stock from a source country — this could be operationalized as edge weight in this network. For instance, shares of multiple destinations (although limited to OECD members number) in French and German FDI stock could be visualized as follows (Fig. 1 and 2):

Having taken a closer look at FDI share distribution among destinations, one could notice that some pattern exists in outward FDI: investors prefer allocating money to one set of countries over another. For instance, FDI outflows from France and Germany are distributed unevenly around the world (aforementioned Fig 1 and 2), and investors' preference for nearby countries (respectively, Italy or Belgium, and Austria or Denmark) is noticeable. This relatively high willingness to invest geographically close to domestic economy, was observed in many cases and called "near-home bias" (Muradoglu, Levis, Vasileva 2010).

Deeper analysis of FDI networks would include exploration of *dynamics* in investment flows after an event, one could expect FDI rebalancing. One of the reasons for this expectation is that similar dynamics has been observed during contagion modeling in interbank financial networks (Elliott, Golub, Jackson 2014; Markose, Oluwasegun, Giansante, 2012; Dungey, Harvey, Volkov 2019) after a money supply shock in the domestic country (e.g. an urgent need to cover other obligations with the funds allocated abroad, i.e. taking money out of overseas projects in order to pay current expenses). As for FDI (not limited to interbank transactions) share, this liquidity stress will result in lower ratio of the overall FDI outflow stock from this donor country.

Fig. 3 and 4. Shares of outward FDI stock made by investors from Germany and France

Following this logic, dynamic perspective could formally presuppose taking post-event deltas — in this case, edges before and after event impact. For researching coronavirus effects the following could be compared: FDI in 2020 against 2021.

Separate edges transformation could also be studied with the OECD database. Like in previous static case, studying edge weights would be a usual step while describing relation *dynamics* between countries. For instance, the relative importance of some German and French investment partners (Fig. 3 and 4) has indeed changed considerably.

Similarly to static case, FDI dynamics from the same country to various destinations diverge considerably. This allocation divergence could be attributed to the aforementioned near-home bias. Mental classification of countries into «near» and «distant» could lead to reticence to close projects in contiguous economies, while pulling resources out of countries on other continents. E.g. this pattern could be traced on the percentile map of Belgian investments (Fig. 5 below).

Clustering in addition to near-home bias

Besides near-home bias, there is more regularity in this non-uniform distribution: investors from some countries demonstrate patterns adding to this near-home bias. Common approach to identifying this structure would be looking for clusters.

Clustering of countries having rising FDI shares (colored in red on subsequent diagrams) would suggest, that their region got preferred rank as a result of investors' "qualculation" process (see «conventions school» of Boltanski, Thevenot and Callon on socially-determined quality evaluation (Boltanski, Thévenot 1991; Callon, Méadel, Rabeharisoa 2002). Capital holders from numerous countries clustered their preferences in Europe, thus revealing Eurocentric focus in their activities.

On the contrary, economies deviating from some standards (accepted by investors) get bad assessments and therefore have decreased FDI share and consequently are located out of this «positive» cluster. Moreover, if these destinations form a cluster with surrounded countries (colored in blue on subsequent diagrams), this similarity could hint a categorization of this whole geographic zone as unattractive (e.g. due to unreliability) and not worthy of investor's attention and resources — some locations could be deemed «territorially stigmatized» (Wacquant, Slater, Pereira 2014).

A suitable algorithm for this approach is LISA (Anselin 1995) — processing local indicators of spatial association for overlaid variables' values on a world map. In order to identify regions in the world with statistically high dependence in neighboring countries the following formula was applied:

$$L = \frac{N}{\sum_j \sum_j w_{ij}} \frac{\sum_i \sum_j w_{ij} (z_i - \bar{z})(z_j - \bar{z})}{\sum_i (z_i - \bar{z})^2}$$

where N is the number of cells/partitions, z_i is the calculated indicator for the cell i , w_{ij} is an estimate of spatial weights reflecting whether i and j are neighbors, such that if they are not, it is equal to zero, and if they are equal to $\frac{1}{|\delta_i|}$, where $|\delta_i|$ is the number of neighboring cells i .

The local indications of spatial association were mapped for the countries with indicators of a level of significance of the p-value at less than 0,05. The given method reveals four types of local clusters: *high-high* is a cluster of spatial autocorrelation of high values in neighboring countries (colored in red on the diagrams below), *low-low* is a cluster of spatial autocorrelation of low values in neighboring countries, *high-low* are the items of high values, appearing in the neighborhood of cluster of low values, *low-high* are the items of low values, appearing in the neighborhood of cluster of high values.

Clustering methods (e.g. the one used during LISA computation), require information about more edges of the worldwide network than provided by the OECD dataset used on previous stages of our study. We should move from analyzing edges set of an individual node (directions of FDI from a country) to revising relations between destination nodes: this technique would allow for completing the connectivity graph with data about non-OECD states as well as OECD members.

In order to move from OECD-limited to the worldwide network, a suitable dataset could be provided by the IMF-made Coordinated Direct Investment Survey (CDIS). This source provides connectivity matrices updated annually, so it is feasible to calculate the change between reported FDI stocks of country i in country j in 2020 and 2021 — like OECD statistics on Fig. 3 and 4 above could be interpreted as increments. This variable should be operationalized as the difference between absolute FDI stock addressed to country j in 2021 vs. 2020, which is taken relative to the overall reported FDI stock (divided by the sum of investments to all the countries).

Before looking for clusters it is worth noticing that improved network connectivity data still allows for finding structures, which do not necessarily form a cluster — e.g. the aforementioned near-home bias judging by links to immediate neighbours of country i . Indeed, the CDIS data makes us believe that near-home bias exists for the variable operationalized above: it will be shown further together with clusters.

Fig. 5 and 6 Increase in shares of Belgian outward FDI stock (percentile map and LISA of IMF CDIS)

Clustering supplementary to the "near-home bias" consequence is demonstrated on Fig. 5 and 6. According to these diagrams, shares of nearby countries in Belgian FDI stock changed mostly in accordance with "near-home bias" hypothesis (increased in contiguous Germany and France). Besides the percentile map, LISA diagram emphasizes that to the North-East from Belgium these shares grew in more FDI destinations, highlighting that in Denmark this value increased along with nearby Norway and Germany.

Fig. 7. Increase in shares of Portuguese outward FDI stock, LISA of IMF CDIS

The largest zone of preferred FDI allocation has been found also visible to the North-East from Portugal (Fig. 7). At the same time, Portuguese investors didn't pay growing attention to Mahreb countries (even though they are located closer than the UK or Denmark).

Conclusion

Not only was FDI near-home bias found several years ago, but also it was identified in FDI destinations rebalancing dynamics after a major event (coronavirus outbreak leading to temporary self-isolation of many economies). This bias could explain divergence in resources allocated to or pulled out of various countries.

Moreover, this uneven distribution of FDI changes between 2020 and 2021 was found to be moderated by cluster patterns spreading beyond first-order neighbours (e.g. many European countries got increasing FDI share from economies located at the other side of their continent).

These clusters could persist in many cases due to institutional and cultural considerations factored into investors' decision-making, which could lead to territorial stigmatization. Reasons for this willingness to finance projects located in neighboring countries could include political stability, which communicate confidence to capital holders.

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